
ENHANCING MIGRANTS' SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC INCLUSION AND LOCAL DEVELOPMENT IN EUROPEAN RURAL AND MOUNTAIN AREAS

Booklet with MATILDE policy recommendations

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Many rural and mountainous areas face different challenges such as demographic change and ageing processes, population decline e.g. due to out-migration of young people or low birth rates as well as different framework conditions, which contribute to labour shortages and by doing so risks of supply insecurity and bottlenecks.

MATILDE assumes that international immigration can be a way to counteract these negative trends in rural areas and be an opportunity for rural development and progress. Therefore, MATILDE focuses on the various impacts of international migration in rural and mountainous areas and how social and economic inclusion of international migrants, especially third-country nationals (TCNs), and rural development can be strengthened.

The MATILDE booklet is a collection of the most essential problems as well as policy recommendations regarding social and economic migration identified in the 10 partner countries.

The identification of key policy issues and the elaboration of corresponding policy recommendations are based on an ongoing analytical process in the MATILDE project. This involved a mixed-methods approach using qualitative interviews, focus groups, quantitative analysis of statistics as well as participatory action research in 13 case study regions with different focal points and involving key stakeholders from different government levels and fields of action.

In particular for the development of policy recommendations, local, regional and national stakeholders were involved in so-called “policy roundtables”. There, based on the aforementioned research and building on a SWOT-analysis (strengths, weaknesses, chances and threats) for the different government levels, pre-validated policy problems, recommendations and solutions were presented, discussed, validated and further developed based on the focus of the respective MATILDE case study region. Hence, a feedback loop of preliminary results with stakeholders and people directly involved in the research still took place during the ongoing project. The co-designing of policy recommendations with relevant stakeholders should also promote subsequent consideration in further policy processes.

The policy recommendations consider the interrelation of different policy fields beyond “integration” policies as well as the migration-rural development nexus. They are promoting measures and governance processes capable to better connect urban and rural/mountainous areas as well as fostering both, rural development and socio-economic inclusion of TCNs. The policy recommendations take into account three dimensions: 1) the different areas of integration (horizontal perspective), 2) the different political levels (vertical perspective; local/regional/national/European), and 3) different groups of TCNs (such as asylum seekers and refugees, migrant workers, persons settling down due

to family reunion etc.). In total, the policy recommendations developed consider ten different „areas of integration“ and have also been assigned to the corresponding level of government. The specific „areas of integration“ are marked with a corresponding symbol in this booklet (see also the explanation of the symbols in the appendix).

Not every country covers policy recommendations for all levels of government. Apart from different focal points of the case study regions that influenced the core topics of policy recommendations, not all levels of government apply to all countries, such as the EU level for Norway or the United Kingdom.

For the MATILDE booklet, the main problems and policy recommendations of the ten partner countries were reviewed and broken down to the most essential ones and collected in a concise form. They are intended to serve as an overview of the situations in the different partner countries and regions. The policy problems and recommendations of each MATILDE country/region listed in this booklet refer to the time of elaboration and validation. When certain topics are mentioned in the policy recommendations, it does not mean that there are no political measures and approaches in this context at all, but that further effort is recommended here.

The booklet consists of chapters divided by countries, each emphasizing the main problems and policy recommendations as well as highlighting a selected policy recommendation that was considered particularly important to that country/region. The concluding chapter presents a summarising collection which offers a cross-country perspective of policy recommendations for the different areas of integration at a glance.

Some of the policy recommendations formulated are not feasible within the current legal frameworks. However, this circumstance was not the claim, but should encourage to reconsider the given framework conditions and, in the best case, to change them in order to enable a positive development.

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AUSTRIA

Authors: Marika Gruber, Jessica Pöcher and Kathrin Zupan

Main Problems	Area of integration
Lack of afternoon child care, full-day kindergarten places as well as resources for kindergartens in rural areas	
Lack of recognition of qualifications as well as long recognition processes	
Lack of (low threshold) encounter of local population and migrants to support the language acquisition and social inclusion	
Difficulties in finding qualified employees	
Labour shortage and de facto no apprenticeship and employment opportunities for asylum seekers due to legal restrictions	
Limited affordability of and discrimination at the private housing market	
Lack of public transport (as TCNs often do not have a driving license) and hence lack of accessibility of public services	
Limited availability and accessibility of language courses in rural and peripheral municipalities	
Lack of cooperation between policy makers, stakeholders, NGOs and volunteers	

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Expansion of integration offices through a migrant intermediary

Local institutions should expand their integration office to include the positions of „intermediary“ with a migrant background, who acts between the institution and the migrant community.

Formation and support of already available communal offers

Communal offers such as open youth work, various learning cafés or sewing workshops provide low-threshold group offers and could serve as meeting places for TCNs and locals. Municipal offers do not exclusively refer to full-time work, but can be coordinated and supported by an municipal employee and operated by actively engaged volunteers.

Creating meeting spaces

Opportunities for joint activities are needed to break down reservations and create a new awareness. It is important that such „spaces“ are made available at the local level, at affordable rents (or even free of charge) and without compulsion to consume, but with a low-threshold approach to reach all population groups.

Local & Regional Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Legislative reform and expansion of childcare services

This policy recommendation aims to promote the adjustment of the childcare ratio (smaller group sizes) and the expansion of kindergarten places (especially in rural communities). Furthermore, the training of pedagogical staff should be increasingly oriented towards diversity, interculturality and multilingualism.

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Strengthening the network between political representatives and stakeholders at all levels of governance

In Carinthia, it is recommended to organise and conduct regular exchange meetings (e.g., roundtables in asylum issues) between representatives of the province of Carinthia, the federal government, municipalities, NGOs, civil society and migrant communities on a regular basis. The aim is to strengthen the multi-level governance of integration in the province of Carinthia. In Vorarlberg, the networking aspect emphasised the continuity of refugee coordinators at the regional level, who serve as contact persons and links for municipalities, volunteers and associations to ensure that central tasks of this function (awareness raising, exchange, counselling, etc.) can also be provided sustainably in small municipalities.

Intercultural training for public administration staff

Local politicians and employees in public administrations need intercultural trainings (e.g. through the Academy of Administration) for a strengthened sensitivity towards diversity, intersectionality and different social target groups.

Development of a information package on housing, social assistance and the labour market

Persons granted asylum and subsidiary protection should receive this information before they leave basic care and asylum accommodation. This information should also be provided in different or relevant languages.

Expansion of public transport in rural and urban areas

Public transport as well as cycle paths should be expanded and financially supported in order to facilitate mobility and thus participation in social life and counteract segregation.

Establishing accommodation in central locations with good accessibility

Well-connected asylum accommodation facilitates with professional care and support, reachable via public transport to facilitate also inclusion in local community life.

National Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

Faster recognition of qualifications and specific education and training offers through further developed institution for holistic recognition of qualifications

Through these measures, potentials for the labour market can be used or promoted more quickly and could also have a positive impact on the integration and economic independence of migrants as well as the satisfaction of regional and local labour market needs. In order to ensure rapid recognition of TCNs' qualifications, a competent institution is needed that saves time and costs and minimises bureaucracy and, based on this, develops and offers specific educational programmes for migrants. Based on an already existing institution such as in Vorarlberg, it is recommended to develop such an institution with an extended focus on formal, informal and non-formal qualifications throughout Austria.

Sustainable reform of the asylum law

Constant amendments to the law should be avoided, as these make the work of civil servants more difficult. Sustainable changes should also include specification concerning the acceleration of the asylum procedures and especially the appeal procedures as well as improving labour market access for asylum seekers, as they can currently only be employed with great bureaucratic effort. (Fast) economic integration would be important, both for their integration process, and to counteract the shortage of labour.

National Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

More trained staff for asylum quarters

The challenges and staff shortages have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 crisis. The ratio of caregivers to asylum seekers in shelters needs to be adjusted to ensure adequate quality.

Better working conditions for caregivers in asylum shelters

Working conditions for staff and quality management need to be improved by providing (more) supervision and introducing minimum standards for qualifications and regular training. This would bring the quality of support in line with the Council of Europe recommendations.

Extending mandatory kindergarten from one to two years

A two-year compulsory kindergarten would help children, especially newly immigrated children, children at risk of poverty etc., to prepare adequately for school, promote their social integration and improve their language skills.

EU Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

Introduction of a quota system

Due to the Dublin Regulation, some Member States are confronted with a high number of asylum seekers at the external borders compared to other Member States without bordering third countries. The quota system is intended to counteract congestion and inequality among the Member States at the external borders (e.g., a compulsory quota up to 1.5% of the total population; penalty fees in case of non-compliance).

Transparency in the distribution of asylum seekers

The distribution should be made transparent, e.g. with a transparency barometer. This would relieve the Member States at the external borders and achieve a fair distribution with an equal use of financial resources.

Improving the quality of EU refugee management

This requires EU wide standards for admission and accommodation of asylum seekers. In addition, a monitoring system must be developed to assess asylum procedures, the quality of asylum accommodation and care, as well as sanctions if Member States continue to violate EU regulations.

Focus on enhanced opportunities for migrants and newcomers in remote regions

Instead of passive observation of „newcomers“ and reluctance to accept them, an open attitude and a focus on the positive aspects and potential of migration, especially for rural regions, should be given priority and migrants should therefore also be given opportunities to integrate successfully.

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Strengthening the network between political representatives and stakeholders at all levels of governance

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BULGARIA

Authors: Chaya Koleva, Anna Krasteva and Vanina Ninova

Main Problems	Area of integration
Lack of public support for social connections and communication between TCNs and locals	
Lack of public transport (regular, inter-village)	
Problematic monolingualism (Bulgaria) in public administrative procedures and on official websites	
Cultural practices are not promoted in several languages	
Lack of Bulgarian language skills due to lack of trainings	
Lack of enough Bulgarian language courses oriented towards migrants in schools	
Lack of support for social enterprises	
Anti-migrant rhetoric of far-right parties	

Local & Regional Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Support of migrants in social and volunteering engagements Many TCNs are socially engaged and oriented to help refugees or to contribute to local development. To support individual initiatives, the municipalities should support them logistically and financially.

Publish in Bulgarian and English on official websites Local events related to art, music, sport and ecology should be promoted on a schedule on the official municipal websites and published in Bulgarian and English language. Information, how to participate or volunteer, should be added.

Improve the transport network The public transport network needs to be improved with more regular inter-village bus lines, in order to make commuting easier and to increase the access to the regional center.

All basic administrative documents to be accessible in English There is a need to provide all basic administrative documents in English (e.g. for the renewal of residence permits) to facilitate the understanding of TCNs who want to stay in the region.

Provide additional Bulgarian language programs Several institutions (e.g. State Agency for Employment, Regional Directorate of Education, municipalities and business sector) should collaborate for providing free courses in Bulgarian language for adults and in schools for children, also after one year of language learning, in order to improve the integration processes of TCNs.

Establish institutional cooperation of active migrants Several TCNs are already promoting the regions as tourist destination and as a place for immigration, which should be supported by the municipalities. Additionally, they should be involved in strategy groups for tourism and migration.

National Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Develop a strategy to attract foreign workers Due to the need of seasonal workers, the State Agency of Employment, the municipalities and the regional businesses should elaborate mechanisms to integrate TCNs in short-term jobs and to offer them vocational trainings depending on the regional economic's needs.

Create and maintain sustainable cooperation to regularly train educators and psychologists A strategy of trainings for school staff should be created to meet the needs of TCNs (children) with traumas and in the need of psychosocial support to improve their development. So they should learn about practices in education, mental health and psychosocial support.

Improve the infrastructure of the refugee camps (for children) The playground in the refugee reception camp needs to be renovated, for what the State Agency for Refugees should allocate funding to create a functional space for art and cultural activities for children.

EU Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Promotion of successful self-employed TCNs and refugees	TCNs and refugees should be supported in setting business plans, applying for funding and with coaching seminars to develop start-ups. They should be invited to European coaching seminars, business forums, job fairs, and intercultural workshops to share their good practices to empower TCNs and refugees business successes contributing to rural development.	
Additional training in Bulgarian for migrant children in schools	Requirements and criteria for Bulgarian language in schools should be established to increase the number of trainings hours, to provide sufficient lecturers and to train the trainers in didactics.	

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Promotion of successful self-employed TCNs and refugees

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FINLAND

Authors: Lauri Havukainen, Pirjo Pöllänen and Daniel Rauhut

Main Problems

High demands on language skills in the Finnish labour market

Current integration legislation neglects, for example, migrant workers and older people in the integration services

Lack of on-the-job learning positions and resources to help the immigrants find those opportunities in small and rural municipalities

Ineffective cooperation between the public sector and the third sector and the instability brought by project-based funding

Area of integration

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Efficient organisation and cooperation in integration work

There is a need for more coherent coordination of integration activities between the different actors, clear roles for municipalities and third sector actors, and adequate coordination between the different organisations working for the integration of immigrants, as well as a better contractual framework for employees working in project-based third sector employment.

Promoting the use of the local language in multicultural associations

In order to create good relations with the population and mutual understanding, the importance of a common language is crucial. Although it may be impractical at first, using the local language will help immigrants from different language backgrounds to communicate better in the long run, but it will also improve relationship building with local stakeholders and encourage local people to participate.

Promoting the local language as a language of integration

As many refugees are also settled in Swedish-speaking areas of the country, Swedish language should be promoted as the language of integration in these areas. Despite the awareness that this is a sensitive political issue, we believe that Swedish should have equal status as a language of integration so as not to compromise the immigrants' ability to integrate into the local community.

Regional Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

More coherent coordination and cooperation between actors at regional level

The local multicultural associations as well as NGOs should have a more organised regional cooperation in which they share information and best practices. In particular, applying for funding would be more effective if these local actors could form larger consortia at regional level.

Consideration of the housing situation and distance when settling refugees

Many rural areas lack adequate housing and public transport, which can pose problems for the integration of refugees and asylum seekers in more remote areas. When settling, the focus should be on ensuring that they, especially families with children, are not accommodated in areas that are far from utilities and where a car is not needed to cope with everyday life.

Diversification of the economic structure to rural regions

The labour requirements of companies must be weighed against the economic benefits, because the use of cheap immigrant labour will delay economic structural change, but not end it. Diversification of the economic structure is needed, as immigrants can play a crucial role. More resources should be made available to improve immigrants' language and academic performance in order to give them the opportunity to improve their socio-economic status.

Improving the marketing of regions' strengths, opportunities and needs

North Karelia and Ostrobothnia have a lot to offer for immigrants but are little known internationally, leading to challenges in attracting migrant workers. The regions must do more and better location marketing and location branding.

National Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

Involving the public sector in setting up on-the-job learning for immigrants

The new curriculum for integration education puts more emphasis on-the-job learning in language teaching. However, this is a demanding task for rural areas, since there are often not enough training places available on the private labour market. The public sector could do more to offer such apprenticeships to immigrants. This should be mandated at national level and it should be an obligation for local authorities.

National policy and support for groups that are left out of integration programs

There should be national guidelines and economic support for local actors on how to substitute the language learning of those migrants who are not involved in the integration courses (e.g., the elderly and labour immigrants) as language learning is often essential for a successful integration.

More stability for the work of the integration course organisers

The organisers of the integration courses are in a conflicted situation due to their integration education program framework contracts (re-tendering every 4 years). They are expected to develop their language teaching, but at the same time they are under pressure to organise the courses cheaply. Organizations need continuity to develop teaching, an extension of the time until the next call for applications and a greater emphasis on qualitative factors such as experience in the application process.

More clarity about responsibilities, rights and expectations in the integration process

It would be beneficial for all stakeholders involved if the kind of aid, how much and for how long the society is providing it, would be communicated better. At the same time, it should also be clarified what is expected of the new residents. If all actors involved know what is expected of them, the outcome, output and impact of the process would improve.

EU Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

Better clarity and accessibility of EU-based funding opportunities

The EU funding instruments for local and regional actors, NGOs should be more accessible and there should be better continuity for project-based activities. At the European level, thought should be given to how small but efficient NGOs could create activities that offer the possibility of more stable and permanent funding.

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Pictures from the case study regions Ostrobothnia and North Karelia

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Efficient organisation and cooperation in integration work.

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GERMANY

Authors: Tobias Weidinger, David Spenger and Stefan Kordel

Main Problems	Area of integration
Disharmonised and inconsistent policies and outcomes	
Lacking knowledge and insufficient communication and bureaucracy for employers	
Negative attitudes, exploitation, racism and discrimination at the workplace	
Lack of affordable and sizable housing lead to concentration processes of TCNs	
Lack of social housing	
Lacking availability of places in nurseries and kindergartens	
Lack of contacts, spaces and time for interactions to reduce cultural barriers	
Negative attitudes towards TCNs and situational hierarchisation of TCNs	
Long travel times despite short distances, high costs and complex ticket systems	
Long decision-making processes for the issuing of visas and the recognition of foreign credentials	

All Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Transparent and clear responsibilities for migration and integration policies

The implementation of policies depends on a clear and transparent share of competences and responsibilities among all government levels. The migration and integration policy implementation should be mandatory with continuous funding and professionalisation processes.

Offer a goal orientation

Instead of a focus on one specific migrant target group, offers should address all immigrants and following, orient on the goal to include several groups of people.

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Engage employers responsibility for international workforce

For the recruitment of international employees it is recommended to use networks of existing staff and of counsellors and target-group specific communication, to recruit multiple persons from the same country and to establish a relocation management. For the onboarding and retention of international employees, regular meetings, tandems or mentoring programs as well as work-accompanying language courses are recommended. Additionally, incentives, e.g. financially, with flexible work models or for long holidays to visit the family, could be beneficial.

Increase childcare and nurseries

Child care is of high importance for the social integration of the children, but additionally a prerequisite for many mothers and single parents to participate in language and integration courses. There is a need for the construction of nurseries and kindergartens and the safeguarding of places in all-day child care and schooling infrastructures.

Foster contacts of migrants and local population

Access to an increased connection is possible in nurseries, kindergartens, schools, workplaces, residential environments, events and festivities accompanied by mediators and bridge-builders. Municipalities should held welcoming receptions for TCNs and parties for their naturalisation and establish welcome hubs. Additionally, clubs and associations could promote themselves in language and integration courses or schools to attract TCNs interest.

Intercultural opening of public administration and services and education and economic players

TCNs can be targeted in different contexts, e.g. asylum accommodation, language courses or migrant associations, and in different forms, e.g. social media or multilingual language. Then, information about rights and responsibilities and offers can be shared easily. Additionally, the staff of administration, services, education and economy should be supported to become intercultural and multilingual.

Strength regional networks and cooperation

Networks and cooperation are needed within and between the Federal States, municipalities, administrations, employers, police, justice system and the civil society, in order to exchange experiences, share demands and develop improvements for TCN's integration. Existing structures should be merged and support from local stakeholders should be gained.

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Regional Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Support for SMEs in recruitment of TCNs

Recruitments of TCNs by SMEs can be improved, e.g. by means of bilateral cooperation. For the recognition of foreign credentials, loans or (partial) waivers for the payment of the processes can be offered to TCNs to reduce the costs. Besides, the recognition processes should be simplified and streamlined.

Improve allocation of asylum seekers and resettlement refugees

The Federal State could apply algorithm-based matching processes to allocate asylum seekers and resettlement refugees to specific rural and mountainous areas. Therefore, the background of TCNs and structural aspects such as the labour market, housing market or existing educational and integration offers need to be considered.

Need for interculturality and multilingualism

The educational staff in schools, nurseries and kindergartens need to know, how to deal with diversity. Therefore, curriculum of prospective teachers could be extended to encompass qualification measures with regard to language education and promotion in the context of migration-related multilingualism.

Establish programmes against racism and for intercultural opening

The Federal State should maintain and consolidate institutions and prevention programmes addressing racism and intercultural opening of society. This includes the Bavarian Information Centre against Extremism (BIGE), the Bavarian State Coordination Office against Right-Wing Extremism (LKS) or the Umbrella Association of the Municipal Integration Advisory Boards in Bavaria (AGABY) respectively the Children and Youth Program of the Bavarian State Government.

National Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Increase funding options in rural regions

In order to relieve the process of accessing and administering funding, the rural districts and municipalities could be assisted with funding consultants. The Federal States could also provide the local level with the opportunity to apply for a 'local integration package' using only one application. The Federal States, then, compile the money from different lines of funding, e.g. from EU, federal and regional level.

Improve access to labour market

In order to support the intercultural opening of the workforce, counselling and information about (recognition of) qualification, education and self-employment should be provided by an expansion of capacities at the authorities. The Federal Government should provide a better communication of opportunities for the recognition of foreign credentials including a less expensive process, check, if work permits for forced migrants can be provided even earlier after arrival than today and evaluate the Temporary Employment Act.

Review three-year residence rule for recognised refugees

The results of the 2022 evaluation of the three-year residence rule for recognised refugees reliant on social welfare need to lead to a comprehensive reconsideration of the rule.

Evaluate requirements for language and integration courses

The minimum requirements for the provision of language and integration courses (including child care offers) could be evaluated to better match the situation in rural and mountainous areas. Therefore, the minimum number of participants/children or the minimum requirements for rooms for the provision of child care offers should be evaluated and offers like the „Integration course with child“ should be extended.

National Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Offer psychological and therapeutical health services	The provision of psychological and therapeutical offers for TCNs in general and forced migrants in particular in rural and mountainous areas needs to be considered as a key for successful settlement and integration. Accordingly, more psychologists and therapists need to be trained and motivated to provide their services outside of the big cities.	
Increase personnel resources in public administration	The embassies as well as the Federal Government should provide more staff for the visa departments respectively the authorities. Then, the visa processes, the recognition of foreign qualifications and the family reunification can be proceeded faster.	

EU Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Implement recognition processes of qualifications	The European Union should facilitate the recognition of professional qualifications to improve the recruitment of skilled workers from third countries, e.g. by means of a directive with defined prerequisites.	
Increase funding for intercultural opening	The European Union should maintain and consolidate funding for the intercultural opening of the workforce (diversity management).	

Implement internet connection as standard in asylum accomodation

It is urgently indicated to define internet connection and Wi-Fi as minimum requirements for asylum accommodation in all Member States of the European Union.

Increase funding for intercultural opening

The European Union should maintain and consolidate funding for the intercultural opening of society, and address the recognition of diversity in rural areas and resulting challenges in funding programmes.

The European Union should dismantle bureaucratic hurdles for small cities and rural districts and municipalities in rural and mountainous areas with regard to applications for EU funding

European Regional Development Funds (ERDF) should increasingly consider migration as a means for economic development, especially in the field of foundational economies, and simultaneously pay attention to social cohesion, which especially becomes challenging in light of transformation processes in the society.

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Pictures from the case study region Free State of Bavaria

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Engage employers responsibility
for international workforce

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ITALY

Authors: Mia Scotti with contributions from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

Main Problems	Area of integration
System of quota for employment that does not meet the labour market needs and generates irregular work exploitation	
TCNs employment is marked by high seasonality, part-time or temporary occupations and rarely self-employment	
Low structured governance and a complex system of not unitary measures and actions characterise Italy's migration and integration policies system today	
The access to essential services is limited in rural regions	
Ineffective and insufficient public transport services	
High share of lower education among TCNs	
Slowness of administrative and bureaucratic procedures and the uncertainty of rules	
Lack of adequate housing	

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Improve the access of TCNs to basic services in housing, mobility, education, welfare and health	Access to basic services, is often reduced in rural and mountainous areas. TCNs are particularly affected by this problem. Therefore, accessible and equal housing policies are needed as well as improved flexible transport mechanism, integrative training including psychological support, welfare actions for families and community managed health services.	
Promote a bottom-up and mutual benefits approach to territorial inclusion respecting the carrying capacity of local communities	In mobility flows are people with different characteristics, which need to be assessed in order to understand, how they can relate to the local contexts. To increase the positive effects, local stakeholders and initiatives should be involved and reception projects started, also to increase the cooperation and contact of newcomers and locals and to reduce mistrusts and fears.	
Enhance a positive socio-economic impact of migration on rural/mountain territories	Main innovative policies should therefore refer to supporting associationism and civic participation at local level and investing on cultural mediators, to be intended as agents of local development, supporting connections between different social worlds.	
Support and valorise workers migrants as an essential resource for local economy and labour system	Specific tools, training and educational paths capable to highlight TCNs competencies should be implemented to continue attracting external workforce in a mutual benefits approach where migrants can have benefits as well. Foreigners should be also supported (when possible) in their formative achievement validation process to access qualified works.	
TCNs and Italian entrepreneurs may be supported in the bureaucratic paths to ask for work permission visa	A more flexible system to access and require work permissions is advocated.	

Regional Level

Regional Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Access to basic services for all (foreigners and not) through well-balanced services plans	Effective public service planning has to be supported and a network of exchange between those responsible for planning and the municipalities who are concerned by the planned services should be institutionalised.	
Institutionalisation of experiences and best practices to standard working practices for all stakeholders in a network approach	Results from different projects should be shared and synergies created between the different stakeholders involved in the inclusion processes. Regions should also encourage the establishment of broad and inclusive partnerships that actively involve all local stakeholders including migrants.	
Ensure mediation and representation of local demands in national arenas by regional administrations	Therefore, linkages between local realities and national decision makers should be fostered and municipalities recognised as active players.	

National Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Reframing migration policies to overcome the emergency approach

An integrated approach should be accompanied by an improved labour market access to contrast irregular work, by an adapted work visa permission system to meet the needs of the local labour markets, by guidance and mentorship for self-employment.

Invest in active demographic policies

The demographic theme and the issue of territorial inequalities must therefore be put in relation with migration policies, within a vision of development of the country centred in a mutual relationship between the centre and the peripheries, and between the different populations living in these territories.

Improve public opinion and political actors' knowledge of the contribution of foreign immigrants to the Italian economy and society

A conceptual framework should be developed with focus on place-based impacts. With a national data policy, data about migration impact can be collected, in order to start a migration impact assessment.

EU Level

Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
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Rethink of European reception policy

The hotspot system and the dynamics of relocation of migration within the Member States should be reviewed to introduce standards and clear definitions.

Promotion of migrant flows including them in development processes and perspectives

This approach would increase the focus on regions.

European regional immigration policy is needed

Europe should have a structural plan with respect to current and future migration flows.

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All pictures on page 48 and 49 are provided by the Italian project partners
 Pictures from the case study regions Bozen and Turin

Reframing migration policies to overcome the emergency approach

NORWAY

Gudbrandsdalen

Main Problems	Area of integration
Lack of viable public transportation system in the mountainous and remote case regions	
Car dependency due to dispersed settlement patterns and public services such as education, health, etc.	
Expensive driver's license and exam hurdles because of language issues	
Lack of access to arenas for social interactions	
High thresholds for labour market participation	
Impediments and scarce support for (aspiring) entrepreneurs	
Limited structured support and procedures for recognition of formal, non-formal, and informal competencies	

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Making information about events and activities more accessible: Local platforms for sharing information	In order to improve access to such information, and consequently expand opportunities for social inclusion, it was proposed to set up community/local level platforms to collect and share information on local events and opportunities. The platform should act as a central information hub for up-to-date information on local activities and opportunities and can not only help to provide updated information to the local population, but may also serve as a strategy to increase the attractiveness of the region.	
Activity Passes and supported leisure activities for migrants and underprivileged youth	Providing children with opportunities to participate in organised activities has an impact on migrant families' access to networks and sense of belonging.	
Inclusion policies and initiatives directed at single-household immigrants	Many of the integration activities and initiatives are mainly aimed at refugee families and children/youth and less at single migrants. This is an important point as we know that single household individuals often feel lonely. Specific suggestion is to include immigrants in activity pass programs, creating informal hangouts for young single adults, and buddy systems that match people with someone of the same age with similar interests.	
Mentors: Door openers to language and social inclusion	The core idea of these programs is that newcomers are matched with a buddy who can help them in a variety of ways, from hands-on language training and cultural understanding to networking and driving practice. These mentors or buddies are intended to act as door openers to Norwegian society and the local community.	
Enhance engagement of the volunteer sector as a supplement to the public refugee services	One strategy to facilitate the development of such collaboration between the volunteer sector and the community refugee services, raised during the idea workshops, was to physically bring the community refugee service together with the local volunteer center through co-location to encourage dialogue and collaboration between these two actors.	

Regional Level

Regional Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Improving migrants' opportunities for geographical mobility	To help migrants obtain a driver's license, which is essential in rural areas, theory courses as well as the driver's test should be offered in different languages. Other initiatives would be improving public transport or setting up ride-sharing systems.	
Establishing a "job central"	The solution to the challenge of labour market inclusion and participation could be the establishment of regional/local "job centres" to complement and work closely with public employment and social central, as well as local businesses. Assisting in assessing and identifying the skills of job seekers (formal and informal) and facilitate access to summer jobs as well as other work experience opportunities.	
Improve access to vocational education opportunities for migrants in rural areas	Integration policies have shifted the focus from quick employment to formal education to secure opportunities for long-term employment. Module-based vocational training is an important element in this shift, and entails development, piloting and testing of more flexible and effective educational programs leading to trade certificates.	
Entrepreneurial courses specifically adapted to immigrants	A way of facilitating entrepreneurship among migrants could be to make relevant information more accessible and to offer entrepreneurship courses specifically tailored to the information needs of prospective migrant entrepreneurs, as well as other forms of support, for example through personal counselling.	

National Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

Documentation and recognition of skills, competencies and education

Structured support and recognition procedures to support immigrants in documenting formal, informal and non-formal skills and competences can be an important solution to facilitate a faster transition into the labour market.

Enhance predictability and communication for local settlement and integration work

Improving the quality of cooperation and communication between central government and local authorities regarding refugee resettlement. There should be more emphasis on the region, when evaluating suitability for resettlement, in terms of job opportunities, mobility, etc. Since this would paint a more realistic picture of the opportunities that are available to those being resettled in smaller, rural municipalities.

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Pictures from the case study region Gudbrandsdalen

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Documentation and recognition of skills, competencies and education

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SPAIN

Authors: Raúl Lardiés-Bosque and Nuria del Olmo Vicén

Main Problems	Area of integration
Difficulties of TCNs in accessing administrative procedures, including online procedures due to the digital gap in terms of knowledge, devices and connectivity in rural areas	
Difficulty of TCNs' access to qualified and long-term jobs, which is why they mainly work in low-skilled economic branches	
Lack of coexistence and acceptance by the local population including stereotypes and stigmas and lack of knowledge about migrants and migration	
Lack of housing in rural areas: little and not available, especially in rural areas and linked to prejudices against foreigners	
Lack of public transport to access public services in rural regions	
Lack of immigration offices in rural areas (due to that they are located in cities) to faster documentation processes; also a lack of officers in these offices is experienced	

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Facilitate the leadership and decision-making of local governments by reforming the local regime and administrative simplification	The reform of the local regime will give more freedom of action to the municipalities and comarcas (groupings of municipalities), and will contribute to increasing social cohesion, without forgetting to reinforce the territorial structure and the cohesion. This differential treatment should be introduced to correct the spatial differences and reduce the gaps between urban and rural areas.	
Establish a housing plan in rural areas with access of foreigners and other vulnerable people	The City Councils should allocate more investment and resources to the creation of housing. More freedom of action in municipalities would allow them to be able to build or rehabilitate more houses in the municipalities, since there are many immigrants and other vulnerable people who must move their place of residence to other nearby with lower prices.	
Offer guidelines for migrants	New arrived people need to know what steps have to be taken and how to carry them out, e.g. requesting residence and work permits, procedures for renting a home, signing up children to schools, accessing health care or how to get a driver's license. Therefore all comarcas should offer guidelines, both in paper and in digital formats.	
Increase the channels of communication	The municipalities could intervene more in organising activities and meeting points for the promotion of a more intercultural coexistence to defeat prejudices, false beliefs and taboos about immigrants. An example would be the creation of (local) radio programs where experiences and initiatives are shown, also giving information about the daily life of immigrants, making their problems visible, but also their achievements.	
Generalise the initiative of intercultural mediators	Intercultural mediators are usually agents and are normally of foreign origin. They work for the reception, orientation and intercultural mediation with foreign seasonal workers for agricultural campaigns and offer help, guidance and explain the services that exist in the area, especially housing and health, to improve integration. For the recommended improvement, EU funding could be received.	

Regional Level

Regional Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Management of social housing for seasonal workers including employer's responsibility	Mobile offices should be established for the management of social housing for temporal workers. With business agreements with employers, they have the responsibility to offer housings for their workers.	
Improve intercity transport and online services	The development of intercity transport is also aimed at structuring the territory and promoting inclusion and social cohesion for all inhabitants of the different areas of Aragón. As an alternative to face-to-face services, the access to online services needs to be improved, in order to overcome immobilities in rural regions.	
Improve the coordination of the public administration	Despite the fact that the 'Forum of Immigration in Aragón' - which brings together the main agents in this matter - is functional in terms of migration, the creation of intersectoral roundtables is proposed for the debate of many problems that concern rural areas and it can be managed from the comarcas.	
Offer language and vocational training	Since there is a need to adapt vocational training to the needs of the sectors with the greatest economic activity in rural areas, the offers of the Adult Education Centers should be expanded. It is proposed to continue training in the Spanish language and to improve vocational training in the main towns of the comarcas, even accompanied by other complementary occupational training (employment workshops).The proposal is to offer these trainings on a rotating basis in the different population centers/towns.	
Develop occupational training	Occupational training courses should focus on the proposal of employers in the area.	

National Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Adapt the Immigration Law to the current Labour Reform (2022)	Currently, to access foreign immigrants to a residence permit, they must justify a minimum employment of one year. The Immigration Law would have to be adapted to the current Labour Reform (2022) to avoid situations of unexpected irregularity as immigrants cannot obtain a new residence permit due to the lack of an employment contract for a minimum duration of one year.	
Increase channels for information and documentation	This can be done by bringing the immigration officers closer to the rural regions, by increasing the allocations for faster processes or by improving online access. Therefore, the form and languages used should be simplified.	
Adapt the national „Catalogue of Occupations with Difficult Coverage“	To meet the local needs, the catalog should include local occupations that are difficult to cover, in order to improve the hiring (a reform of this catalog at the national level is currently being carried out in 07/2022).	
Recruit at origin	The recruitment of foreign workers at their origin should be promoted (a reform of this aspect is currently being carried out in 07/2022).	
Improve cooperation	The cross-cutting nature of migration requires the participation of the entire organic structure of the state and all levels of public administration. Given the nature of the decentralised model, it is considered a priority to increase coordination in multilevel management and multilevel governance.	

EU Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration
Harmonise asylum procedures	Asylum and migration management should take a more global approach, be more efficient and better able to cope with migratory pressures so that the distribution of applicants among countries is more equitable. They should thus be harmonised and immigrants should thus be distributed fairly according to the capacity of each country.	
Extend the presence of Frontex	To reduce the problems of human trafficking between Morocco and Europe, it is recommended to intensify and extend the presence of Frontex operations not only in the Canary archipelago and other EU borders.	

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Establish a housing plan in rural areas with access of foreigners and other vulnerable people

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SWEDEN

Dalarna

Main Problems

Area of integration

Employment gap between migrants and natives is among the highest in OECD-countries

Gender gap between TCN men and women in terms of employment and earnings

Unemployment among foreign-born in Dalarna

Difficulties in matching labour needs with job seekers in Dalarna

Parts of the region has limited public communications

MAIN PROBLEMS

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Strengthen measures that offer language training in combination with work

The initiative „SFI combination“, offers language training in combination with training (e.g. welder or cook). It is recommended to use and further develop existing good examples of these offers and to improve the possibilities and knowledge of employers to offer work in combination with language training.

Develop the work on inventory of local labour market opportunities

An important part of the local preparedness is to consolidate current knowledge about the local labour market, about the companies' needs, about which meeting places there are and how they can constitute important pillars in the integration work.

Work to reduce the differences between women's and men's participation and performance

Develop measures that make it easier for women to participate in the activities of the induction programme even if they have young children.

Strengthen work that focuses on public health, as this is essential for cohesion and a sustainable working life

Encourage participation in sports, outdoor activities or similar. One example from one municipality is the leisure-check: Each child in the municipality, regardless of background, up to the age of 15 receives a check for SEK 500 each year to use for sports or leisure activities, such as membership in an association or entry to the swimming pool.

Regional Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Scrutinise and consolidate the co-ordination of integration measures on a regional level

At the regional level, a decision should be made as to which body should be responsible for coordinating and setting up a communication platform between all those involved in #integration work in Dalarna.

Use existing structures and networks to spread knowledge of good practices

Use existing structures and networks to spread knowledge of good practices between municipalities and local enterprises and promote continuous learning, even if municipalities and local enterprises may depart from diverse contexts.

Build on already existing examples from the region to develop solutions for more efficient public transport in rural areas

A goal should be to promote stronger connections between rural and urban areas and to improve the mobility options of rural people in general and those without access to a car in particular.

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National Level

Policy Recommendation

Short Explanation

Area of integration

Consolidation of competencies and knowledge with regard to Municipal labour market integration offices and the Swedish Public Employment Service

The consolidation of knowledge about people and industries serves as a basis on which to work with local matching. Existing knowledge says that networks are important for access to jobs and these are created in local contexts and environments where many people come together.

Ensure offers of physical meetings with the Swedish Public Employment Service

Physical meetings promote interaction, the use of public space and the expansion of knowledge and experience. In quantitative terms, consider the number of physical offices and physical meetings with jobseekers.

Strengthen initiatives where work experience and language learning are integrated and increase the possibilities for employers to offer work in combination with language training

Improvement here is to increase and facilitate cooperation among municipalities so that individuals can learn more about opportunities in other places. In this way, access to more specialised education would improve.

Strengthening local education provision; increase cooperation and adapting to the needs of the local labour market

Continue and develop existing work that involves dialogues with public and private employers, and their possibilities to have an impact on provision of education and training.

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Pictures from the case study region Dalarna

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Strengthen measures that offer language training in combination with work

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TURKEY

Main Problems	Area of integration
High informality of migrant labour in precarious and unsafe work environments	
Lack of regulations in the Labour Law regarding rural jobs	
Difficulties with Temporary Protection Status	
Shortage of labour force at local labour markets and need of international workforce	
Precarious housing conditions in removable tents	
Increasing school dropouts among migrant children due to language barriers and contribution in households income	
Health services are limited in rural regions	
Limited contacts of migrants with locals due to state of temporariness, ghettoisation, anti-migrant attitude and tensions among vulnerable groups	
Political participation is linked to the Turkish citizenship, which is characterised by discretionary and complex process of naturalisation	
Depopulation is problematic also due to uncontrolled industrialisation and urbanisation	

MAIN PROBLEMS

Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Provide sustainable accommodation for migrants

The local municipal actors and the local representatives of the central state actors should work together with local employers to organise sustainable accommodation facilities for seasonal migrant workers with minimum quality and safety standards.

Initialise new projects in agri- and eco-tourism via cooperation

Agri- and ecotourism is a growing demand, which can be met with financial opportunities to develop projects and via cooperation of business associations, municipalities and agricultural producers. The agriculture can additionally be equipped with smart technologies.

Embrace a rights-based approach in communicating with migrants

Ensuring their equal and fair access to labour market procedures and the facilitation of full access to legal aid should be among the major priorities.

Increase contacts of migrants and locals

In order to achieve social cohesion of immigrants with the native populations, local municipalities can organise get-together meetings at the local level in different neighbourhoods where there is a critical mass of migrants.

National Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Preventing child labour

The Ministry of National Education should collaborate with the relevant local actors, land owners and producers should be informed and trained about the negative consequences of child labour. Local actors and international institutions should collaborate to offer educational and child-care services to the migrant communities.

Revision of the Labour Law

The rights of migrants should be recognised, e.g. by improving the employment opportunities of migrants and refugees.

Engagement of Labour Unions for seasonal workers

Workers abused by third parties and/or employed as cheap labour force may establish associations or unions to protect their rights. The presence of both, Turkish and immigrant-origin workers, in such unions would be purposeful. Additionally, the image of agricultural workers and rural jobs can be improved via these channels.

Sustainable access and disposition in education

Increase childcare access, prevent school dropouts and increase language course opportunities.

Access to health services

Arabic interpreters should be available at all hospitals and government offices, and hospital staff should be trained regarding migrant needs.

Engaging the media

The local branch of Directorate Migration Management should work on a communication strategy to appeal to the local media promoting solidarity and human protection values, with biographies and refugee testimonials, and an explanation of how they relate to all of the native population.

Develop long-term perspectives for rural sustainable development

Through the cooperation of state actors, laws (e.g. 6360, 5216) should be reviewed to invest in agricultural production and increase resources for villages. Additionally, climate change should be discussed in this frame to include it in short-term planning.

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Embrace a rights-based approach in communicating with migrants

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UNITED KINGDOM (SCOTLAND)

Authors: Michele Bianchi, Maria Luisa Caputo and Simone Baglioni

Main Problems	Area of integration
More difficult and complex recruitment in the fishing industry due to the new migration policy and the end of the EU free movement	
Depopulation of Scottish rural areas and ageing population	
Absence of a social housing strategy that can respond to the needs of the local economy and to the demographic challenges	

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Local Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Officially co-design new investment plans for social housing involving local economic actors together with the HHP and the City Council

The future investment plan of the HHP (The Hebridean Housing Partnership) should be linked to the plan for the development of local businesses and harmonise both strategies. There is a need to link the need for new social housing with the current need for new labour and the future investment and expansion plans of local business actors.

Promote opportunities for foreign workers to attend ESOL courses to learn English

Local authorities can support English language learning by reactivating language courses and ESOL (English to Speakers of Other Languages) courses for foreign workers. These can be organised in consultation with employers to help workers optimise their daily routines.

Development of a local programme to support the settlement and integration of migrants, using public sector expertise and private and third sector resources

This will ensure that every job opportunity in the Western Isles is linked to housing and integration opportunities. This will help migrants cope with the daily challenges of living in rural areas and facilitate their access to services and resources.

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National Level		
Policy Recommendation	Short Explanation	Area of integration

Development of a programme to promote settlement in rural areas by offering jobs, accommodation, access to necessary local services and other employment opportunities

There is a need for a programme at the regional level that aims to create local partnerships between the private, public and third sectors to provide integrated solutions to settle and support newcomers and their families in remote areas. This must include access to affordable accommodation within reasonable distance of employment, as well as opportunities and facilitation of language learning, access to basic services and social and economic opportunities.

Development of a local-based system for settlement and integration

Approach that focuses on recruiting migrants with the occupations, skills and demographic profiles that best contribute to sustaining local businesses and communities.

Enabling a regional list of shortage occupations

This is to facilitate the arrival of newcomers so that they can be employed in the sectors where there is the greatest need in the area.

A new policy to recognise the challenges faced by the fishing industry in the West of Scotland in terms of recruitment and assure its survival

This will facilitate the recruitment and arrival for workforce in these areas and avoid workers' exploitation.

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Pictures from the case study region East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland

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Development of a local-based system for settlement and integration

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The preceding chapters described the policy recommendations that were developed by the scientific case study teams in cooperation with the local partners for the different government levels (local, regional, national and European Union) and the individual fields of action based on empirical results of different work packages which were discussed, supplemented and validated in the roundtables. In the following chapter, the individual recommendations for action are summarised by field of action across the MATILDE countries. On the one hand, this overview summarises the most important recommendations collected per field of action. On the other hand, this thematically ordered overview gives an impression, simply in terms of the number of recommendations, which fields of action proved to be particularly important.

Some topics and recommendations for action are important from the perspective of several MATILDE countries and regions. This is indicated in the following overview by the fact that several country codes are listed for this recommendation.

The summarised overview of recommendations for action is based on the results of the individual country chapters in this booklet. Hence, no new or additional recommendations

for action are listed here, but rather a cross-country thematic overview is given.

For more information on the MATILDE Policy Recommendations, see also the MATILDE Policy Briefs (Deliverable D6.3) on „The Impact of Migrants on Rural Development“, „Migration as Chance for Rural Economies“, „The Interplay of Rural Regions, Migration and Legal Frameworks“, and „Better Education of (young) TCNs as Basis for Economic and Social Integration in Rural Areas“, as well as MATILDE Deliverable D6.4 – Multi-dimensional policy-recommendation matrix.

Authors: Marika Gruber and Jessica Pöcher

Economy & Employment

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

AT	Legislative reform und expansion of childcare services
AT, DE, NO	Faster recognition of qualifications and specific education and training offers through further developed institution for holistic recognition of qualifications
BG	Develop a strategy to attract foreign workers
BG, NO	Promoting successful self-employed TCNs and refugees and entrepreneurship courses specifically tailored to immigrants
DE	Engage employers responsibility for international workforce
DE	Support for SMEs in recruitment of TCNs
DE, TR	Revision of the Labour Law and Improve access to labour market
DE	Increase funding for intercultural opening
ES	Adapt the national „Catalogue of Occupations with Difficult Coverage“

Economy & Employment

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

ES	Recruit at origin
FI	Diversification of the economic structure to rural regions
FI	Improving the marketing of regions' strengths, opportunities and needs
FI	Involving the public sector in setting up on-the-job learning for immigrants
FI	More stability for the work of the integration course organisers
IT	Support and valorise workers migrants as an essential resource for local economy and labour system
IT	TCNs and Italian entrepreneurs may be supported in the bureaucratic paths to ask for work permission visa.
NO	Establishing a "job central"
NO	Improve access to vocational education opportunities for migrants in rural areas

Economy & Employment

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

SE	Strengthen measures that offer language training in combination with work
SE	Develop the work on inventory of local labour market opportunities
SE	Work to reduce the differences between women's and men's participation and performance
SE	Consolidation of competencies and knowledge with regard to Municipal labour market integration offices and the Swedish Public Employment Service
TR	Embrace a rights-based approach in communicating with migrants
TR	Preventing child labour
TR	Engagement of Labour Unions for seasonal workers
UK	Enabling a regional list of shortage occupations
UK	A new policy to recognise the challenges faced by the fishing industry in the West of Scotland in terms of recruitment and assure its survival

Education

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

AT, DE	Reform of legislation and expansion of childcare and nurseries
AT	Extending mandatory kindergarten from one to two years
BG	Create and maintain sustainable cooperation to regularly train educators and psychologists
DE	Need for interculturality and multilingualism
DE	Evaluate requirements for language and integration courses
ES	Develop and Offer language, vocational and occupational training
IT, NO, TR	Improve access to vocational education opportunities for migrants in rural areas
SE	Strengthen initiatives where work experience and language learning are integrated and increase the possibilities for employers to offer work in combination with language training
SE	Strengthening local education provision; increase cooperation and adapting to the needs of the local labour market

Health

Country Code	Policy Recommendation
DE	Offer psychological and therapeutical health services
IT, TR	Improve the access of TCNs to basic services in housing, mobility, education, welfare and health

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Housing

Country Code	Policy Recommendation
AT, TR	Establishment and provision of sustainable accommodation for migrants in central locations with good accessibility
DE, FI	Consideration of housing situation and distance in the settlement of asylum seekers and resettlement refugees
DE	Review three-year residence rule for recognised refugees
DE	Implement internet connection as standard in asylum accomodation
ES	Establish a housing plan in rural areas with access of foreigners and other vulnerable people
ES	Management of social housing for seasonal workers including employer's responsibility
IT	Improve the access of TCNs to basic services in housing, mobility, education, welfare and health
UK	Officially co-design new investment plans for social housing involving local economic actors together with the HHP (The Hebridean Housing Partnership) and the City Council

Language & Culture	
Country Code	Policy Recommendation
BG	All basic administrative documents to be accessible in English
BG, UK	Offer additional language programmes and promote opportunities for foreign workers to learn the local language
BG	Improve the infrastructure of the refugee camps (for children)
BG	Additional training in Bulgarian for migrant children in school
DE	Intercultural opening of public administration and services and education and economic players
FI	Promoting the use of the local language in multicultural associations.
FI	Promoting the local language as a language of integration

Mobility

Mobility	
Country Code	Policy Recommendation
AT, BG, IT, NO	Expansion and improvement of public transport in rural and urban areas
ES	Improve intercity transport and online services
SE	Build on already existing examples from the region to develop solutions for more efficient public transport in rural areas

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Rights & Citizenship

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

AT, ES	Strengthening networking and cooperation between political representatives and stakeholders at all levels of government
AT	Intercultural training for public administration staff
AT	Development of an information package on housing, social assistance and the labour market
AT	Sustainable reform of the asylum law
AT	More trained staff for asylum quarters
AT	Better working conditions for caregivers in asylum shelters
AT	Introduction of a quota system
AT, IT	Rethinking European reception policies and transparency in the distribution of asylum seekers
AT	Improving the quality of EU refugee management

Rights & Citizenship

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

AT	Focus on and enhance opportunities for migrants and newcomers in remote regions
DE	Increase personnel resources in public administration
DE, ES	Offer guidelines and goal orientation for migrants
ES	Facilitate the leadership and decision-making of local governments by reforming the local regime and administrative simplification
ES	Adapt the Immigration Law to the current Labour Reform (2022)
ES	Increase channels for information and documentation
ES	Harmonise asylum procedures
ES, FI	More coherent coordination and cooperation between actors at regional level
FI	Efficient organisation and cooperation in integration work

Rights & Citizenship

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

FI	National policy and support for groups that are left out of integration programs
FI, DE	More transparency and clarity on responsibilities, rights and expectations for migration and integration policy and the integration process
FI	Better clarity and accessibility of EU-based funding opportunities
IT	Access to basic services for all (foreigners and not) through well-balanced services plans
IT	Reframing migration policies to overcome the emergency approach
NO	Enhance predictability and communication for local settlement and integration work
SE	Strengthen work that focuses on public health, as this is essential for cohesion and a sustainable working life
SE	Scrutinise and consolidate the coordination of integration measures on a regional level
SE	Use existing structures and networks to spread knowledge of good practices
SE	Ensure offers of physical meetings with the Swedish Public Employment Service

Rural/regional development

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

BG	Establish institutional cooperation of active migrants
DE, TR	Strengthen regional networks and cooperation and initialise new projects in agri- and eco-tourism
DE	Increase funding options in rural regions
DE	The European Union should dismantle bureaucratic hurdles for small cities and rural districts and municipalities in rural and mountainous areas with regard to applications for EU funding.
IT	Institutionalisation of experiences and best practices to standard working practices for all stakeholders in a network approach
IT	Ensure mediation and representation of local demands in national arenas by regional administrations
IT	Invest in active demographic policies
IT	Improve public opinion and political actors' knowledge of the contribution of foreign immigrants to the Italian economy and society
IT	Promotion of migrant flows including them in development processes and perspectives

Rural/regional development	
Country Code	Policy Recommendation
TR	Develop long-term perspectives for rural sustainable development
UK	Development of a local programme to support the settlement and integration of migrants, using public sector expertise and private and third sector resources
UK	Development of a programme to promote settlement in rural areas by offering jobs, accommodation, access to necessary local services and other employment opportunities
UK	Development of a local-based system for settlement and integration

Safety & Stability	
Country Code	Policy Recommendation
ES	Extend the presence of Frontex
IT	European regional immigration policy is needed

Social Connection & Cohesion

Country Code	Policy Recommendation
AT	Expansion of integration offices through a migrant intermediary
AT, NO	Establish and support existing community services and expand volunteering to complement public refugee services
AT, DE, TR	Creating meeting spaces and foster contacts of migrants and local population
BG	Support of migrants in social and volunteering engagements
BG, ES	Publish in national language and English on official websites
DE	Establish programmes against racism and for intercultural opening
DE	Increase funding for intercultural opening
IT	Improve the access of TCNs to basic services in housing, mobility, education, welfare and health
IT	Promote a bottom-up and mutual benefits approach to territorial inclusion respecting the carrying capacity of local communities

Social Connection & Cohesion

Country Code

Policy Recommendation

IT	Enhance a positive socio-economic impact of migration on rural/mountain territories
NO, ES	Making information about events and activities more accessible: Local platforms for sharing information
NO	Activity Passes and supported leisure activities for migrants and underprivileged youth
NO	Inclusion policies and initiatives directed at single-household immigrants
NO	Mentors: Door openers to language and social inclusion
TR	Engaging the media

Pictogram	Area of Integration
	Economy and employment
	Education
	Health
	Housing
	Language & culture
	Mobility
	Rights & Citizenship
	Rural/regional development
	Safety & stability
	Social connection/cohesion
	Main Problem
	Policy recommendations

Country	Code
Austria	AT
Bulgaria	BG
Finland	FI
Germany	DE
Italy	IT
Norway	NO
Spain	ES
Sweden	SE
Turkey	TR
United Kingdom	UK

MATILDE

Migration ImpAct assessment To Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European rural and mountain regions

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